

Microbial colonization and associated health risks

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Background

The surface of microplastics (MPs) offers a high microbial cell density and increased nutrient availability, creating "hot-spots" for microbial colonization in the aquatic ecosystems. This colonization can include toxic, pathogenic, or invasive species. Since MPs can be transferred over long distances in aquatic ecosystems horizontally and within water columns (vertically), they may act as efficient vectors for selecting and spreading pathogenic and other harmful microbes. One concerning aspect is that MPs can facilitate the horizontal gene transfer (HGT) of genetic material among microorganisms. HGT is a mechanism by which genetic information, such as antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs), can be transferred between different species of bacteria. This process plays a significant role in the spread of antibiotic resistance, which poses a serious threat to human and environmental health.

In this context, we are studying the microbial colonization and potential transfer of ARGs on the surface of different plastic types, including tyre wear particles (TWP). TWP, in particular, is noteworthy due to its composition, which includes heavy metals. These heavy metals present in TWP could contribute to the co-selection and dissemination of ARGs, further exacerbating the issue of antibiotic resistance.

Work performed

Preparation of tyre wear particles (TWP)

The tyre wear particles (TWP) were collected from the treads of the three most commonly used automobile tires in Germany. The particles were obtained by scrapping and shaving the tire treads using scrubbers. Subsequently, the scraped particles were subjected to a washing process and sieved through stainless sieves with pore sizes of 200 μm and 10 μm , resulting in the isolation of TWP ranging from 10 μm to 200 μm in size. The sterilized TWP were then stored in a glass bottle at room temperature.

Characterization of tyre wear particles (TWP)

Polymer type identification

The μ FTIR (Fourier Transformed Infrared) spectroscopy analysis was carried out to identify the polymer composition of TWP. The absorption spectra of FTIR confirmed the functional groups belong to the polystyrene and styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR) in TWP.

Quantification of heavy metals in TWP

The heavy metal composition of TWP was determined by HNO_3 (70%) digestion method. The heavy metals were in the following order of concentration $\text{Zn} > \text{Si} > \text{Al} > \text{Fe} > \text{Mg} > \text{Pb} > \text{Cr} > \text{Cu} > \text{Mn} > \text{Co} > \text{Cd}$ with Zinc exhibiting the highest concentration (73441.89 ± 12472 mg/kg \pm SD).

Heavy metal	Concentration	Standard deviation
Zn	73441.89	12472
Si	7136.71	734
Al	1976.91	386
Fe	929.99	101
Mg	607.42	65
Pb	90.02	32
Cr	46.24	15
Cu	42.85	9
Mn	33.01	8
Co	32.12	10
Cd	2.56	2

Table. Heavy metal concentration (ppm) in tire wear particles analysed by ICPMS.

Fig. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra of the tyre wear particles (TWP)

Heavy metal release over time

The leaching of heavy metals from TWP in DEV medium (10 g/L Meat Peptone, 10 g/L Meat Extract, 5 g/L NaCl) were measured by incubating the tubes over a period of 48 hours at 30 °C. The heavy metal analysis was carried out by ICP-MS. Among the total heavy metals observed in TWP, aluminum, manganese, cobalt, copper, zinc, and cadmium were observed to leach. The total concentration of these leached heavy metals showed an initial increase after 12 hours, followed by a relatively stable concentration until 36 hours. Subsequently, a gradual decrease in concentration was observed.

Fig. Total heavy metal release from tire wear particles (TWP) ($\mu\text{g/L}$) into the nutrient broth over 0, 12, 24, 36 and 48 h of incubation.

Toxicity testing of heavy metals

The heavy metal toxicity was determined based on growth inhibition of *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas* which consisted of measuring changes in bacterial densities through absorbance measurements at 600 nm after 24 hours of incubation. The bacteria were exposed to a mixture of heavy metal concentrations each of 0.01, 0.1, 1 and 10 ppm. Each concentration was tested in triplicates along with control without the heavy metals. The heavy metal mixture consisted of the metals found during the leaching experiment. No significant effect on the growth of *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas* was found at the doses tested.

Standardizing the conditions for HGT

Gene transfer model used

To study the HGT via conjugation, *E. coli* MG1655 with IncP-1 3 broad host range (BHR) plasmid pJK5::*gfpmut3* was used as a donor. A *Pseudomonas* sp. previously isolated from Lake Stechlin was used as a recipient strain. In addition, the natural lake microbial community was also used as a recipient. Donor cells due to the presence of a *laclq-LppmCherry-km^R* gene

cassette in chromosome gives red fluorescence whereas a recipient receiving plasmid (transconjugant) results in green fluorescence due to *gfp* gene expression. The proportion of transconjugants:donor (T/D) or transconjugants:recipient (T/R) indicated the gene transfer frequency. The plasmid exchange activity was analyzed by flow cytometry (FACSriaII instrument) and fluorescence microscope (Zeiss Axio Imager).

Fig. Horizontal gene transfer (HGT) activity analysed by Flow cytometer (FACSriaII instrument).

Fig. Donor cells (left) and transconjugants (right) under the fluorescence microscope (Zeiss Axio Imager).

Effect of temperature on HGT in the presence of TWP

The TWP (60 mg L^{-1}) were incubated with the donor and recipient (1:10) at 17, 20, 25, 27 and 30 °C for 24 hours. A control without TWP was kept at each temperature.

In general, higher temperatures resulted in a significant increase in the number of conjugation events (T/R or T/D) with the highest frequency of HGT occurring at 30°C among the temperatures tested (Kruskal-Wallis test, $H = 13$, $p = 0.01$). There was no plasmid exchange at 17 °C and 20 °C. Conjugation was not observed in the planktonic phase, except at 30 °C where it exhibited a 2.6-fold decrease compared to the particle phase. The overall plasmid exchange at 30 °C was 17-fold increase than the control.

Fig. HGT at different temperatures in the presence of TWP.

Fig. Top panel (A1, A2, A3) represents the cells grown at 25 °C. A1 represents total cells stained by DAPI, A2 represents only the donor cells (*E. coli*) expressing red fluorescence *mCherry-km^R* gene and A3 represents the transconjugants expressing *gfp* gene fluorescence. Similarly, the lower panel (B1, B2, B3) corresponds to the cells grown at 30 °C in the presence of tire wear

particles. The encircled zone in the lower panel shows the tire wear particles as hot spots of biofilm formation and gene exchange.

Effect of incubation time on HGT in the presence of TWP

The TWP (60 mg L^{-1}) was incubated over 24 h and 48 h with donor and recipient (1:10) at 30°C , with respective controls without TWP. There was a significant difference in the HGT frequency between 24 and 48 hours of incubation with the highest transfer events recorded in 24 hours (Wilcoxon pairwise comparison test, $p = 0.007$).

Fig. Ratio of transconjugants and recipients over 24 and 48 h of incubation in the presence of TWP

Effect of donor:recipient on HGT in the presence of TWP

Five different ratios of donor and recipient cells (1:10, 1:100, 1:1, 10:1, 100:1) were selected to assess the effect on HGT frequency. There was a significant difference in HGT frequency between different ratios ($p = 0.0006$). The T/R showed a significantly higher frequency in the 1:10 and 1:100 proportions among all the ratios. However, there was no significant difference in T/R of 1:10 and 1:100. The transfer frequency (T/R) in 1:10 and 1:100 was around 27 times higher than the lowest frequency measured in 100:1 treatment.

Fig. Ratio of transconjugants and recipients at different ratios of donor and recipient

Comparing the gene transfer activity on TWP with polystyrene, heavy metals and chitosan

Five treatments were assayed: a) TWP at 60 mg/L concentration (TWP); b) PS at 60 mg/L concentration (PS); c) heavy metals (Al = 0.16 ppm, Mn = 1.40 ppm, Co = 0.0006 ppm, Cu = 0.16 ppm, Zn = 0.069 ppm and Cd = 0.00021 ppm) (HM) d) Chitin (CH) and e) control containing nutrient broth DEV only.

There was a statistically significant difference in HGT frequency among the different treatments tested with the highest transfer rate found in TWP ($p < 0.05$). Ratios (T/R) measured from bacteria on TWP ($4.5 \pm 1.3 \times 10^{-3}$, mean \pm SD) were around 27 times higher than those of bacteria in the surrounding medium of the same treatment ($0.168 \pm 0.25 \times 10^{-3}$, mean \pm SD) while there was no activity found in the treatment without particles. Comparing heavy metal (HM) ratio with other groups other than the TWP, there was significantly higher activity in the heavy metal treatment ($p < 0.05$) ($0.23 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-3}$, mean \pm SD).

Fig. HGT in TWP (tire wear particles), PS (polystyrene), HM (heavy metals), CH (chitosan) and Ctrl (control).

HGT in lake microbial community

The TWP (60 mg/L) were incubated with the *E. coli* (donor) and the lake microbial community (Lake Stechlin, Germany) as (recipient) in the ratio of 1:10 at 20 °C and 25 °C for 24 hours. The DEV nutrient broth was added as an additional nutrient source in a ratio of 1:1000 to the water sample. Treatment without TWP acted as a control.

The plasmid transfer rates (T/R) measured on TWP at 20 °C ($1.37 \pm 0.062 \times 10^{-3}$, mean \pm SD) were 49.7 times higher than those of planktonic bacteria in the same treatment ($2.74 \times 10^{-5} \pm 3.7 \times 10^{-5}$, mean \pm SD) and significantly higher than the control treatment, without TWP ($p = 0.005$). At 25 °C, the plasmid transfer ratios (T/R) measured on TWP were highly significant compared to those of planktonic bacteria in the same treatment and the control treatment without TWP ($p = 0.005$). The HGT transfer rate on particles at 25 °C was 87.6 (T/R) times higher than 20 °C.

Fig 5. Biofilm formation and antibiotic resistance gene exchange on tire wear particles with natural lake microbial community as recipients. Top panel (A1, A2, A3) represents the cells grown at 20 °C. A1 represents total cells stained by DAPI, A2 represents only the donor cells (*E. coli*) expressing red fluorescence *mCherry-km^R* gene and A3 represents the transconjugants expressing *gfp* gene fluorescence. Similarly, the lower panel (B1, B2, B3) corresponds to the cells grown at 25 °C.

HGT in bioplastic and their non-bioplastic counterparts using *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* as a recipient

Among the three bacterial isolates received from the Plastic Fate partners (*Vibrio parahaemolyticus*, *Pseudomonas monteilii* and *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*), *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* showed the highest plasmid acceptance efficiency.

Standardizing the conditions for HGT

Effect of donor:recipient on gene transfer

Five different ratios of donor (*E. coli*) and recipient cells (*Vibrio parahaemolyticus*) (1:10, 1:100, 1:1, 10:1, 100:1) were selected to assess the effect on HGT frequency. There was a significant difference in HGT frequency between different ratios ($p = 0.0006$). Since the number of donor and recipient cells varied on the particles, the ratio of transconjugant and total number of cells (donor and recipient cells) was chosen for analysis. The plasmid exchange was seen highest in 10:1 proportion among all the ratios.

Fig. Ratio of transconjugants and total cells at different ratios of donor and recipient

Effect of abundance on gene transfer

The impact of varying cell densities, measured in terms of OD600, on the frequency of plasmid transfer was examined. The results indicated that higher cell densities or abundance promote gene transfer activity

Fig. Plasmid transfer activity at different cell abundances

HGT activity in bioplastic and their non-bioplastic counterparts

Different bioplastic and their non-bioplastic counterparts which were selected to study the HGT included Bio-HDPE, Bio-PLA, PHBV, HDPE Bottle, PLA bottle and PET. Chitosan was selected to represent a control mimicking the natural aggregates in the aquatic ecosystems. These plastic types at conc. of 100 mgL⁻¹ were incubated with *E. coli* and *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* at 30 °C for 24 h. The HGT was noticed both in the particle and the liquid part of the sample. The number of cells of both the recipient and the donor on particles varied among different treatments.

Fig. The cell number of recipients (left) and donors (right) on the particles of different plastic types

The number of cells of both donors and recipients was similar among all the treatments except in the chitosan samples.

Fig. The cell number of donors (left) and recipients (right) in the liquid suspension of different plastic types

Considering the variation in the number of donor and recipient cells across the treatments, the horizontal gene transfer (HGT) was calculated by taking into account the total cell count. There was a significant difference among all the treatments with the highest gene transfer rate in the PLA-bottle.

Fig. HGT in different bioplastic and their non-bioplastic counterparts.

Key points

1. The TMP contained heavy metals (Al, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Cu, Zn, and Cd) with an increased total concentration after 12 hours in the medium, remaining similar until 36 hours.
2. Heavy metal concentration in TMP didn't show any toxicity to the bacteria (*Pseudomonas* and *E. coli*).
3. TWP promotes the horizontal gene transfer between donor *E. coli* and recipient *Pseudomonas*.
4. Heavy metals in TWP were found to be one of the reasons for HGT in TMP
5. The transfer frequency is affected by the temperature, incubation time, and the ratio of the bacteria.
6. Donor (*E. coli*), when incubated with a natural lake microbial community in the presence of TMP, showed a significant increase in HGT frequency which was affected by temperature. An increase in temperature promoted the HGT frequency.

Future tasks

1. Comparing the plasmids IncP pJKJ5 and RP4 for gene exchange in the presence of different plastics.
2. Study the biofilm formation of bacterial isolates *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*, *Pseudomonas monteilii* and *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* on different plastic types
3. To investigate the molecular mechanism of HGT in the bacterial isolates in the presence of different microplastics

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